

On a simple and fast thresholding method for spike sorting

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Abstract: Through spike sorting, information about the neurons' activity is acquired via extracellular recordings of action potentials. In this work, a simple and fast approach based on the standard deviation of a channel's recording for the detection of the neurons' signals (spikes) is presented and evaluated. Furthermore, an analysis concerning data filtering is done. The results indicate that the performance of the detection approach strongly depends on the spike density. With lower densities, filtering and higher thresholds return adequate results. At higher densities, different parameters make nearly no differences.

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I. Introduction

Spike sorting is a method to analyze extracellularly recorded action potentials of neurons after which information about the activity of single neurons is extracted. Applications include research and treatment of neurological disorders, investigating responses to stimuli, and neural prosthetics [1]. The correlation-based spike sorting algorithm from Larionov et al. showed promising results with its high efficiency and low computing times [2]. It was recently further improved by adding a graphical user interface and optimizing its spike detection method [3]. Originally, the spike sorter used a primitive threshold approach based on the spike prominence where signals were labeled as spikes if they crossed a certain, fixed threshold. However, since this approach does not consider outliers in the noise and fails to detect spikes with lower amplitudes at the same time, a more sophisticated method for spike detection was needed [4]. In this paper, the performance of simple and fast approach combined with a digital lowpass filter is presented.

II. Material and methods

To assess the performance of different spike detection methods, data is generated to know the ground truth. The data is then used for spike detection and two parameters are extracted.

II.I. Spike train generation

The extracellular brain recording data are simulated by a python-based algorithm. The modelled spikes and Gaussian white noise are used to simulate spike trains obtainable by multichannel extracellular brain recording. With this approach, it is known when simulated neural activity occurred. For each of the three different spike densities and four different noise levels, ten different datasets were generated, totaling up to 120 different datasets. The noise levels were calculated as the ratio

between the noise's standard deviation and the mean amplitude of the placed spike types.

II.II. Spike detection

To test filtering effects on the spike sorting process original and filtered data are compared. The data, generated with a sampling rate of 20 kHz, are imported, and, in case of filtering, a digital filtering with a Butterworth filter of the 5th order and a cutoff frequency of 3 kHz is applied. Then, the 2.5th or 3rd standard deviation of each channel is set as each's threshold, and the spikes' necessary prominence is defined. The prominence specifies how much a spike needs to stand out from surrounding data points. After detecting peaks that cross the threshold and have required prominence, duplicated spikes are eliminated since spikes can show multiple prominent side lobes.

II.III. Spike validation

A simple method to assess detected spikes is to take the simplified generated spike train that contains the values 0 and 1 (Fig. 1 B) and multiply it with a train with only zeros and where all detected spike peaks are labeled with the value 1 (Fig. 1 C). This results in a spike train with only correctly detected spikes (Fig. 1 D). The sum of the train from Fig. 1 C is the number of detected spikes, the sum of the train from Fig. 1 D is the number of correctly detected spikes. The number of placed spikes is given by the spike generator. The two examined parameters are the ratio between correctly detected spikes and all detected spikes as well as the ratio between all detected spikes and placed spikes.

III. Results and discussion

For lower spike densities, the performance of the simple and fast thresholding approach, which is based on the standard deviation of a channel, increases with a higher threshold and filtering as shown in Figs. 2-3.

Figure 1: Main steps of the spike validation. (A) Generated spike train. (B) Validation keys of spike train. (C) Train of all detected spikes. (D) Train of correctly detected spikes. Note, that the third spike is not detected.

At higher noise levels, the standard deviation increases slightly which raises the threshold a little bit. At lower spike densities, where noise is relatively more present, it leads to a higher overall detection rate with lots of falsely detected noise peaks (see Figures 2 and 4). With higher spike densities, the performance of the new approach does not change with the different thresholds or filtering. Since there are more spikes present, the standard deviation is naturally larger, and the threshold is at a higher level. This enables the detection of only signals with high amplitudes and prevents the false interpretation of noise outliers as spikes. As it can be seen from Figure 3, practically all detected signals were spikes. However, it should be noted that not all spikes could be detected because spikes with a lower amplitude do not cross the higher threshold level (s. Figure 5). The detection rate decreases slightly in Figure 5 compared to Figure 4 with increasing noise levels because a higher level raises the threshold further. Thus, some spikes with higher amplitudes will not be recognized anymore compared to the lower noise levels while noise is still not strong enough to be detected as spikes. Only when the threshold is set lower and the signal is not filtered, more spikes will be detected because some noise is falsely identified as spikes. The spike sorter’s better detection performance for low-pass filtered signals is probably due to a better signal-to-noise ratio, thus appropriate filtering of signals is recommendable and will be a feature of the next spike sorter version.

Figure 2: Ratio between correctly detected spikes and all detected spikes across different noise levels with a spike density of 10%.

Figure 3: Ratio between correctly detected spikes and all detected spikes across different noise levels with a spike density of 50%.

Figure 4: Ratio between all detected spikes and placed spikes across different noise levels with a spike density of 10%.

Figure 5: Ratio between all detected spikes and placed spikes across different noise levels with a spike density of 50%.

IV. Conclusions

The presented fast and simple spike detection approach shows promising results. Especially the use of a digital lowpass filter increases the performance of the detection. Nevertheless, future work should focus on an approach to circumvent the spike density-dependency of our spike sorter’s thresholding approach.

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